

Sources of Information and Students' Use of Tobacco in Secondary Schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria

Levi Udochukwu Akah

Department of human Kinetics and Health Education, University of Calabar, Nigeria

Email: leviakah@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study assessed information sources as per the use of tobacco among secondary school students in the area of study. Two specific objectives were of interest to the researchers. In accomplishing the objectives, the study adopted the survey research design. The population of the study comprised 6,361 students from 77 public secondary schools in the study area. Two sampling techniques (stratified and proportionate simple random sampling) were used in selecting a sample of 620 respondents from 25 secondary schools in the area. The instrument used to gather relevant information for the study was a questionnaire. The instrument was analysed for reliability using the Cronbach Alpha method, with an acceptable internal consistency index of .864. Two research questions were structured and answered using percentage. The result of the analysis indicated that the health warning, written on the packet of cigarette, significantly influenced students' use of tobacco. Advertorial channels through which students access information on cigarette smoking significantly influenced students' use of tobacco. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that sources or channels through which students access information on cigarette smoking significantly influenced their use of tobacco. The study recommended that the government should encourage the health warning written on the packet of cigarette. Again, the Government should ban advertorial channels through which students' access information on cigarette smoking.

Keywords: Advertisement, cigarette, health, information, students, tobacco.

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Introduction

It is a generally accepted fact that the youths of today are the leaders of tomorrow. Hence, it is necessary to promote good health among them so that they can pursue their dreams and subsequently partake in the task of nation-building. Tobacco can be in smoke or smokeless form. The most common form of smoke tobacco is a cigarette. Smokeless tobacco includes tobacco products such as moist snuff, chewing tobacco, and snuff. Every smokeless tobacco package and advertisement will include one of the following warning label statements: "warning that this product can cause mouth cancer"; "warning that this product can cause gum disease and tooth loss"; "this product is not a safe alternative to cigarettes"; "smokeless tobacco is addictive"; "warning that smokers are liable to die young". The warning label statement must

be located on the two principal sides of the package and cover at least 30% of each side. For advertisements, the warning label statements must cover at least 20% of the area of the advert. These are aimed to increase awareness of the health risks associated with tobacco use and improve public health.

With the advent of restrictions on tobacco advertising in many developed countries, cigarette packaging has become a major avenue for tobacco companies to promote their product. There are many cigarette brands and distinguishing between them can be difficult for buyers. Cigarette packaging consequently assists consumers to select among other relatively homogenous products and influences the decision-making of the consumer. Corporate branding is a well-established marketing tool for generating customer loyalty and this is especially true. For tobacco, cigarette brands enjoy the highest brand loyalty of all consumer products, with less than 10% changing brands annually.

Cigarette smoking has been referred to as a paediatric epidemic whose addictive nature ensures that most smokers who initiate smoking in their childhood will continue the habit into adulthood (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (USDHHS), 1994). This is buttressed with the finding that in the United States, 80% of adult smokers become habitual smokers before the age of 18 and 90% before the age of 20 (Centers for Disease Control, CDC, 1998). It is unknown how this pertains to Africa, but Howell (2009) showed that most students in Africa who were current smokers, initiated smoking between the ages of 12 and 14 years. Individuals who started smoking at younger ages are more likely to become strongly addicted to nicotine (CDC, 1994), and have an increased risk of developing lung, kidney, and bladder cancer as well as coronary heart disease (CDC, 1998).

The issue of tobacco consumption among secondary school students in Nigeria should be an issue of serious concern to all parents, teachers and students. This concern is not only based on the overly harmful health effects of smoking but also the apt observation that the epidemic of cigarette smoking is already shifting from the developed countries to developing countries. Smokers initiate long-term addiction, with likely major health consequences later in life. Widespread use of robust marketing tactics suggests that the marketing managers are insensitive and unmindful of the health dangers of their products to the consumers. Despite the domestication of the WHO's Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) and subsequent enactment of the Anti-Tobacco Law in Nigeria. There seems to be an unchecked high prevalence of smoking among the youths. trying to checkmate the ethical issues associated with tobacco use promoted this study, hence, it is set to assess the ethics of health warning written on the packet of cigarette and advertorial channels on the use of tobacco in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Health warning on the packet of cigarette and the use of tobacco

Health warnings on cigarette packs have been found to inform smokers about the health hazards of smoking, encourage smokers to quit, and prevent non-smokers from starting to smoke.

Warnings on tobacco products are an ideal way of communicating with smokers because they pair the warning directly with smoking behaviour. According to the U.S. Surgeon General health warnings on cigarette packages are a direct, cost-effective means of communicating information on the health risks of smoking to consumers. According to the Institute of Medicine (Hammond et al., 2013), restrictions on package labelling are critical to reducing tobacco use and ensuring that smokers are adequately informed about the risks of smoking. Health warnings were first required on cigarette packs by the Federal Cigarette Labelling and Advertising Act of 1965. The current health warnings consist of four text-only messages that have appeared on cigarette packs since 1985.

A posit from Eniojukan (2015) indicated that health warnings are intended to change social norms about tobacco use, which will reduce tobacco use and increase support for tobacco control measures. Effective health warning labels provide direct health messages to smokers to raise awareness of health risks, which increases the likelihood they will reduce or quit tobacco use. Large and graphic pictorial warnings that cover at least half of both the front and back of tobacco packages are more effective than smaller or text-only warnings (WHO, 2011). Warning labels have greater public support than most other tobacco control interventions and can be implemented at virtually no cost to the government. A piece of advice from WHO (2011) indicated that the health effects of tobacco use should be described in specific and be periodically rotated to maintain their impact. Deceptive terms suggesting that some products are less harmful (e.g., light or mild) should be banned. Plain (standardized) packaging enhances the impact of health warnings and other packaging and labelling measures.

In an investigation to show the implicit motivational impact of pictorial health warning on cigarette packs, Volcan (2013) revealed that stamped warnings antagonized the appeal of the brands by imposing a cost to manipulate the cigarette packs, especially for smokers. Participants' judgments according to the study revealed that the more aversive a warning, the more it is perceived as effective against smoking. Additionally, Rekha and Anjum (2012) findings show that people of both lower and middle socioeconomic status are more in favour of the implementation of the warnings compared with the higher socioeconomic status groups. The finding also showed that the graphic warnings tend to be more effective among people from a lower socioeconomic status than in those of a higher socioeconomic status. The graphic warnings are somewhat more effective among people in the lower than people in the higher socioeconomic status groups in prompting action (Rekha and Anjum, 2012).

Advertorial channels and the use of tobacco

Advertorial channels here refer to any source through which students acquire (contact) information on tobacco (cigarette) smoking. The channels range from social media, newspaper, television programmes, use of celebrities and famous athletes. Among men, some radio exposure and high radio exposure were associated with increased odds of any tobacco use, compared with no radio exposure. Among men, infrequently reading newspapers/magazines and frequently reading newspapers/magazines were associated with higher odds of smokeless

tobacco use, compared with not reading newspapers/magazines. Among women, infrequently reading newspapers/magazines was associated with reduced odds of smokeless tobacco use, compared with not reading newspaper/magazines. According to the WHO (2011) report on the Global Tobacco Epidemic, of the 445 million people (6.3% of the world's population) who live in one of the world's 100 largest cities, almost 99million (in 20 cities) are exposed to graphic pack warnings.

Many countries have successfully passed partial limitations on tobacco advertising. In the mass media studies have found that partial bans do not affect sales. For example, Stewart (2006) found no effect of television advertising bans and concluded that advertising does not affect sales. Alternatively, Stewart's study might be interpreted as evidence that partial advertising bans simply result in substitution to other media or promotional methods. Chinenye et al. (2017) that the mass media have enormous potentials to influence health-related behaviours and perceptions. Adebola et al. (2012) conducted a study on Mass media exposure, social stratification, and tobacco consumption among Nigerian adults. Their result shows that approximately 4.2% of Nigerian adults used tobacco 2.7% smoked tobacco whereas 1.5% used smokeless tobacco. Tobacco use was more prevalent among men than women. Haines-Saah et al. (2015) observed that social media is a potent commercial channel used by many industries. The main objective of this study was to assess sources of information and Tobacco use among secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone. Specifically, the study assessed whether:

- i. Writing on the packet of cigarettes that smoking is dangerous to health influence smoking among Secondary School Students in Calabar.
- ii. The information on tobacco products from advertorial channels influence cigarette smoking among Secondary School Students

Research questions

The study was guided by two research questions

- i. To what extent does the writing on the packet of cigarettes (that smoking is dangerous to health) influence students' smoking behaviour in secondary schools?
- ii. What is the extent to which the information on tobacco products from advertorial channels influence cigarette smoking among Secondary School Students?

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study is the survey design. According to Kerlinger and Lee (2000), survey research is a systematic empirical inquiry, in which the scientist does not have direct control of the independent variables because their manifestations have already occurred or because they are inherently not manipulable. Inferences about relations are made without direct intervention from concomitant variations of the independent variable. The survey research design is deemed appropriate for the study because it allows for the retrospective examination of the independent variables. The population of the study comprised all 6361

public secondary school students from 77 public secondary schools in the Calabar Education Zone (Ministry of Education, Calabar, Cross River State, 2015). The sampling technique adopted for this study was the stratified random sampling technique. The stratification was based on the different Local Government Areas. While proportionate simple random technique to determine the percentage of respondents from each Local Government Area sampled for the study 20% of schools from each Local Government Area were sampled for the study. The sample for this study is made up of 620 respondents randomly selected from 25 schools in the study area.

Ethical issues and Students' Tobacco Use Questionnaire (EISTUQ) was the instrument used to gather relevant information for this study. The questionnaire is a self-reporting instrument developed by the researcher with a guide from the help of two Measurement and Evaluation experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Calabar. The instrument is made up of two parts: 1 and 2. Part 1 elicited personal background information from the respondents. Part 2 was divided into three sections, A, B, and C with a focus on health warnings, advertorial channels and tobacco utilization, respectively. The responses in A-C were structured on a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly disagree. To ensure the face validity of the instruments, the researcher submitted draft copies of the instrument to five experts (three Test and Measurement experts and two health education experts) all in the Faculty of Education, University of Calabar.

The experts scrutinized and edited the items. This led to the removal of items ambiguously and vaguely structured. With all these inputs made, a final instrument was produced for the study. The questionnaire was subjected to trial testing using fifty (50) students from the zone who were not involved in the study but shares the same characteristics with the study population. The responses were analysed using the Cronbach Alpha reliability method to obtain internal consistency. A coefficient of .864 was a sufficient justification that the instrument had an acceptable reliability index.

The questionnaire was administered to the respondents at the sampled schools. The respondents were adequately briefed on the importance of the study. They were also assured of the confidentiality of their responses. Letters of introduction were collected from the Head of Department for permission to the schools selected. This exercise lasted for three weeks out of 618 copies of the questionnaire administered only 579 were completed and retrieved and were used as the sample for the study. A key was developed to serve as a guide for coding the data that would be collected for statistical analysis. The different parts of the questionnaire were coded differently to suit its purposes. Information on part 1 was coded and scored as discrete data.

Results

Research question one

To what extent does writing on the packet of cigarettes (that smoking is dangerous to health) influence smoking among Students in Secondary Schools? To answer this research question, items 24-34 of the questionnaire were analysed using simple percentage. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Response of the respondents on whether writing on the packet of cigarettes that smoking is dangerous to health influence smoking among Secondary School Students in Calabar(N=620)

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES				Total %
		A f	%	D f	%	
24	I observed each cigarette pack has health warnings alert on cigarette foil (wrapper)	245	39.52	375	60.48	620 100
25	I have notice health warning alerts accompany jingles each time cigarette is advertised on our television and radio	230	37.10	390	62.90	620 100
26	Health warning on the dangers of smoking cigarette are inscribed on bill boards in community	253	40.81	367	59.19	620 100
27	I read in a newspapers where tobacco customers are reminded that smoking is dangerous as it causes cancer	206	33.23	414	67.77	620 100
28	I have read the warning on cigarette package that tobacco can cause gum disease and tooth decay	372	60	248	40	620 100
29	I observed that each cigarette pack has a warning that 'smokers are liable to die young'	399	64.35	221	35.65	620 100
30	The warning on cigarette pack is usually written on the two sides of the package	245	39.52	375	60.48	620 100
31	The warning on label is usually located on the two principal sides of the cover of cigarette pack	230	37.10	390	62.90	620 100
32	I observe that warnings on majority of cigarette pack I come across were positioned face down	253	40.81	367	59.19	620 100
33	Warning on cigarette packs are not really necessary because it will not deter me from smoking if I want	206	33.23	414	67.77	620 100
34	I suggest the warning on cigarette packs be removed	372	60	248	40	620 100

From Table 1, it can be observed that 245 (39.52%) agreed that they observed each cigarette pack has health warnings alert on cigarette foil (wrapper), while 375 (60.48%) do not. Also, 230 (37.10%) agreed that they notice health warning jingles are broadcast each time is

advertised on our television; while 390 (62.90%) do not. Also, 253 (40.81%) agreed that Health warning alerts on cigarette are inscribed on strategic places in our school bar and the city I live, while 367 (59.19%) do not. Also, 206 (33.23) agreed that they read in a newspaper where tobacco customers are reminded that smoking is dangerous as it causes cancer, while 414 (67.77%) do not. The result also shows that 372 (60%) of the total respondents agreed that they have read the warning on cigarette package that tobacco can cause gum disease and tooth decay, while 248 (40%) do not. Also, 230 (37.10%) agreed that they observed each cigarette pack I come in contact bears health warnings alert on it warning that smokers are liable to die young; while 390 (62.90%) do not. Also, 253 (40.81%) agreed that the warning label statement is usually located on the two principal sides of the package of a cigarette, while 367 (59.19%) do not. Also, 206 (33.23) agreed that the warning label statement is usually located on the two principal sides of the cover cigarette package, while 414 (67.77%) do not. Also, 253 (40.81%) agreed that they observed the majority of cigarette pack I come in contact with were positioned face down showing the large pictorial warning, while 367 (59.19%) do not. Also, 206 (33.23) agreed that they observed the majority of cigarette pack I come in contact with were positioned face down showing the large pictorial warning, while 414 (67.77%) do not. Finally, 399 (64.35%) agreed that they suggest the warning on cigarette packs be removed, while 221 (35.65%) do not. The results of the analysis indicate that the percentage of disagreement for all six items are higher than so. This implies that writing on the packet of cigarettes that smoking is dangerous to health influence smoking among Secondary School Students in Calabar.

Research question two

What is the extent to which information on tobacco products from advertorial channels influence cigarette smoking among Secondary School Students? To answer this research question, items 35-44 of the questionnaire were analysed. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Response of the respondents on whether information on tobacco products from advertorial channels influence cigarette smoking among Secondary School Student (N=620)

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES				Total %
		A f	%	D f	%	
35	Newspaper	380	61.29	240	38.71	620 100
36	Television	345	55.65	275	44.35	620 100
37	A show featuring celebrities	330	53.23	290	46.77	620 100
38	Sports competition	401	64.68	219	35.32	620 100
39	Radio	395	63.71	225	36.29	620 100
40	Movie	412	66.45	208	33.55	620 100
41	Face book	330	53.23	290	46.77	620 100
42	YouTube	401	64.68	219	35.32	620 100
43	Wikipedia	395	63.71	225	36.29	620 100
44	WhatsApp	412	66.45	208	33.55	620 100

The result in Table 2 shows that 380 (61.29%) agreed that Newspaper, while 240 (38.71%) do not. Also, 345 (55.65%) agreed that Television, while 275 (44.35%) do not. Also, 330 (53.23%) agreed that Musical show featuring celebrities; while 290 (46.77%) do not. Also, 401 (64.68%) agreed that Sports competition; while, 219 (35.32%) do not. Again, 395 (63.71%) agreed that Radio, while 225 (36.29%) do not. Also, 345 (55.65%) agreed with that movie, while 275 (44.35%) do not. Also, 330 (53.23%) agreed that Facebook; while 290 (46.77%) do not. Also, 401 (64.68%) agreed that YouTube; while, 219 (35.32%) do not. Again, 395 (63.71%) agreed that Wikipedia, while 225 (36.29%) do not. Finally, 412 (66.45%) agreed that WhatsApp, while 202 (33.55%) do not. The result of the analysis, indicate that the percentage of agreement for all five items are higher than 50. This result, therefore, signifies that information on tobacco products from advertorial channels influence cigarette smoking among Secondary School Student.

Discussion

The result of the first research question indicated that the health warning is written on the packet of cigarette significantly influenced students' use of tobacco. The findings are in line with the view of Rekha and Anjum (2012) who observed that people of both lower and middle socio-economic status are more in favour of the implementation of the warnings compared with the higher socio-economic status groups. The finding also showed that the graphic warnings tend to be more effective among people from a lower socioeconomic status than in those of a higher socioeconomic status. The graphic warnings are somewhat more effective among people in the lower than people in the higher socio-economics status groups in prompting action. One possible explanation for this finding is that people from lower socio-economic groups may have been previously unaware of the ill effects caused by tobacco usage.

The findings also show that 81.3% of the study subjects felt that the government needs to introduce much stronger messages such as graphic pictures of cancer to make these warnings more effective. These findings are comparable with the observations that the government needs to introduce much stronger messages such as dreadful pictures of cancer to make these warnings more effective as current warnings appearing on tobacco packs at present are weak and ineffective, which will not perform the crucial role of informing users and saving lives. Also, about 73.2% of the subjects felt that graphic warnings need to cover 100% of the cover page to make these warnings more effective. The findings also show that only 21.9% of the study subjects tried to quit their tobacco-related habits after the introduction of pictorial warnings.

Eniojukan (2015) also pointed out that the influencing role of smoking adverts has been well explored and reported. Of greater significance is the observation that the majority of the respondents were well aware of the warning advert that cigarette smokers are liable to die young. Notwithstanding this level of awareness, smokers in this cohort remained adamant not to quit smoking apparently because they enjoyed smoking and they observed that there were people who smoked and yet enjoyed a long life. These are very wrong and negative perceptions

that need to be corrected through education and counselling. Their knowledge of the health effects of smoking may not be adequate as it has been shown in a study that there is a correlation between knowledge of health effects of smoking and smoking status; those that smoked had poor knowledge while those students with good knowledge never smoked a cigarette.

Health warnings on cigarette packs have been found to inform smokers about the health hazards of smoking, encourage smokers to quit, and prevent nonsmokers from starting to smoke. Warnings on tobacco products are an ideal way of communicating with smokers because they pair the warning directly with smoking behaviour. According to the U.S. Surgeon General health warnings on cigarette packages are a direct, cost-effective means of communicating information on the health risks of smoking to consumers. Given the reach and frequency of exposure, warnings have the potential to have a significant impact on smoking behaviour. For example, a pack-a-day smoker could be exposed to the warnings more than 7,000 times per year. Consequently, warnings on cigarette packages are one of the most important sources of health information. According to the Institute of Medicine, restrictions on package labelling are critical to reducing tobacco use and ensuring that smokers are adequately informed about the risks of smoking. Indeed, prominent health warnings on packages are among the most cost-effective forms of public health education available.

Health warnings were first required on cigarette packs by the Federal Cigarette Labeling and Advertising Act of 1965. The current health warnings consist of four text-only messages that have appeared on cigarette packs since 1985. In the 30 years since the implementation of these warnings, their effect on smokers has drastically weakened, and the current warnings are now virtually ineffective. These warnings are small and easily overwhelmed by the designs on cigarette packages. Warning labels have greater public support than most other tobacco control interventions and can be implemented at virtually no cost to the government. WHO (2011) advised that they should describe specific health effects of tobacco use and be periodically rotated to maintain their impact. Deceptive terms suggesting that some products are less harmful (e.g., light or mild) should be banned. Plain (standardized) packaging enhances the impact of health warnings and other packaging and labelling measures.

The result of the second research question indicated that, advertorial channels through which students' access information on cigarette smoking significantly influenced students' use of tobacco. The findings are in line with the view of Haines-Saah, Kelly, Oliffe, Bottorff (2015) who observed that social media is a potent commercial channel used by many industries. One of the effects of anti-tobacco regulations was a push for innovation in tobacco marketing. One of the recent attempts to establish an overview of tobacco marketing activities in social media has analyzed a set of 70 popular cigarette brands segmented into two groups by their retail prices. The search has been conducted across Facebook, YouTube and Wikipedia using brand names as keywords. Youth is a crucial target audience for both tobacco marketing and anti-tobacco campaigns. According to the research, tobacco advertising reaches via social media 11% of youth. Tobacco promotion exposure via social media was associated with an increased positive attitude towards tobacco smoking.

Hard-hitting anti-tobacco mass media campaigns increase awareness of the harms of tobacco use, reduce tobacco use, increase quit attempts, and reduce second-hand smoke exposures. Campaigns should be sustained over long periods to have a lasting effect, although more limited campaigns can have some impact if run for at least a few weeks. Despite the expense involved, mass media campaigns are very effective at reaching large populations quickly and efficiently. Television advertising with graphic imagery is especially effective in convincing tobacco users to quit. Nearly 3.8 billion people (54%) of the world's population live in countries that have aired at least one national and tobacco mass media campaign on TV and/or radio for a duration of at least three weeks in the past two years. However, about half of the countries in each income group have not used any national mass media campaigns in the past two years to inform people about the harms of tobacco use or encourage them to quit.

Chinenye et al. (2017) also noted that the mass media have enormous potentials to influence health-related behaviours and perceptions. The study sought to explore how World Tobacco No Day was framed in the print media and smoker journalists' attitude towards coverage of the event. Three privately-owned national dailies were studied to find themes dominating reports on World No Tobacco Day and to find the prominence given to the reports as well as sources of such stories. Twenty-two smoker journalists were also surveyed to find their attitude towards coverage of the event. It was found that World No tobacco day was not given enough prominence by the selected newspapers and the majority of smoker journalists will be uncomfortable covering the event. It was recommended among others that the Nigerian press should give priority attention to the coverage of world No Tobacco Day issues in the country.

Comprehensive bans include a ban on the use of the names, logos, and trademarks of tobacco products in any medium under any circumstances, including advertising for any product or event. These names may be used as part of the product packaging. Games, prizes, and free distribution are also prohibited. The ideal approach to estimating the effects of comprehensive bans is an econometric model, which would hold constant all other factors that affect consumption, such as price, income, and other economic or cultural variables. In addition, comprehensive bans are most likely to be legislated along with a series of other restrictions on tobacco, such as limitations on places where smoking is allowed, health promotion sponsorship foundations, health education programmes, and counter-advertising

Adebola, Kasisomayajula, Ichiro, David and Williams (2012) also showed that approximately 4.2% of Nigerian adults used tobacco 2.7% smoked tobacco whereas 15% used smokeless tobacco. Tobacco use was more prevalent among men than women (12% vs. 0.6%; p -value 0.0001). Gender modified the associations between tobacco use and radio exposure or TV exposure (p values ranged = 0.02-0.05). Among men, some radio exposure and high radio exposure. Among men, infrequently reading newspapers/magazines and frequently reading newspaper/magazines were associated with reduced odds of smokeless tobacco use compared with not reading newspaper/magazines. They went further to conclude that relationships between mass media exposure and tobacco consumption differed by

gender and were more pronounced among men. Research on radio programmes may help to form policies that can address tobacco use among Nigerian men.

Despite the achievement recorded in Nigeria since the FCTC, there is still a long way to enforcement and compliance with some major sections of the FCTC in Nigeria. These sections include Article 5.3 (Industry Interference), Article 6 (Price and Taxation) and Article 13 (Advertising). Using the protocol for observational and reportorial data gathering as identified by the Framework Convention Alliance (FCA), data gathering was conducted on Article 13 and 6 in three states representing the three regions in Nigeria. The states are Lagos, Enugu and Abuja.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluding that health warning is written on the packet of cigarette and advertorial channels through which students access information on cigarette smoking significantly influenced students' use of tobacco.

Recommendations

It based on this that the study highlighted recommendations:

1. Government should encourage escalate the health warning written on the packet of cigarette through the Ministry of Health and other health promotion agencies.
2. Government should ban advertorial channels through which students and minors access information on cigarette smoking.

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